

EFFECT OF FRYING CONDITIONS ON THE SENSORY PARAMETERS OF BARBEQUE SEASONED POTATO CHIPS

¹Subhashini Mohandoss, ²Sameera Nayani, ²R G Math

¹Department of Food Technology and Management, MOP Vaishnav College for Women, Nungambakkam, Chennai-600034, Tamil Nadu
Email: subhashinimohandoss@gmail.com

²Samath Global Food Consultants Pvt Ltd, Uppal, Hyderabad-500039, Telangana

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ABSTRACT

The research aims to determine the effect of time and temperature for frying sun-dried potato chips with different compositions of barbeque-flavoured seasoning over various sensory parameters and the oil absorption rate. Potato chips were fried in oils heated to 190, 200, and 210 °C in two batches of time t_1 and t_2 ; the fried chips then were seasoned with the barbeque flavour of 3 different formulations which is of varied combinations of sweet and spice levels. The measurements included oil absorption rate and sensory analysis.

The results of the study showed that the amount of oil absorbed was dependent on the time and temperature of frying of the potato chips, in which the least oil absorption rate was shown by the chips fried at 190 °C at time t_1 . The analysis of sensory attributes indicated that the flavour, colour, texture, and taste of SS_3 formulation of the barbeque seasoning had a more appreciated and acceptable sensorial score.

Keywords: potato chips, time and temperature, sensory analysis, oil absorption, barbequeseasoning

INTRODUCTION

The potato (*Solanum tuberosum*), which is grown in over 100 countries around the world, is a staple of the human diet and is the world's fourth largest staple crop, after maize, wheat, and rice, with 381 million tonnes produced worldwide in 2014. Potato chips are a popular and preferred fried snack worldwide to their flavourful taste and processability (Singh and Kaur, 2016; Osiriphun et al, 2018) In 2020, the global potato chip market was worth 31.2 billion USD. The market is predicted to increase moderately between 2021 and 2026. While 86 per cent of customers in the United States and France consume potato crisps, closely followed by 84 percent of British consumers, China is at the opposite end of the spectrum, with only 28 percent

consumption. The processed potato industry has responded by manufacturing lower fat 'oven fried' chips and developing low-oil content manufactured snacks and potato chips. Depending on the variety of potatoes and the processing methods, the oil content ranges from less than 30% to more than 40% by weight because of the typical fat absorption during deep-fat frying, fried products may have a large amount of fat or oil (Gamble et al, 1987; Hatem et al, 2012). As a result of the recent trend of lowering the fat content of fried dishes, low-fat foods are being developed and there have been numerous attempts to minimize the oil absorption rate during deep-fat frying. Several pre-frying processes have been developed in order to limit the quantity of absorbed oil in fried potatoes, making such items more

appealing to health-conscious consumers and in this case, controlling the ultimate oil content of a high-oil-content snack is critical to maintaining consumer acceptability (Pedreschi and Zuniga, 2009; Gamble and Rice, 1988). During frying, the water in the raw material evaporates and is partially replaced by oil, which accounts for up to 40% of the completed product and so influences its qualities (Kita et al, 2005). Sun drying biological food commodities requires simultaneous heat and mass exchanges, in which heat propagates throughout the product and water migrates from the interior to the surface, where it evaporates. Hence, this method was adopted to make low-fat potato chips.

Materials and methods

Preparation of Materials

Sun-dried potato chips were procured from a food processing company and potato slices of 1.3-1.7mm thickness were separated which was optimized based on prior testing evaluating the effect of thickness on the sensory parameters. No other pre-treatment was undertaken except for blanching with no chemicals before dehydration of potato slices using the sun drying method. The barbeque seasoning was developed with the list of ingredients given in table 1 after numerous trials with four different variations (SS₁, SS₂, and SS₃) in the formulation with different spice and sweet levels. Procurements

Table 1: Formulation of Barbeque seasoning

Ingredients	Formulation (in %)
Base mix	63
Flavour dry mix	9
Spice & sweetness	28

Frying

Deep frying was carried out in a thermostatically temperature-controlled fryer with a feed oil ratio of 1:50. The chips were fried in batches of 25gms of weight with sunflower. The frying temperatures were set at 190 200 and 210° for two sets of time t₁ and t₂ (70 seconds and 80 seconds respectively), and the time was recorded using a stopwatch.

Figure 1: Flowchart for preparation of barbecue seasoned potato chips

Seasoning coating

The potato chips after frying were sprayed with not more than 15% hot oil, then seasoned using a coating pan with a capacity of 0.5kg with an attached oil sprayer.

Sensory analysis

The three variants of barbeque seasoned potato chips were sensorially evaluated by seven panelists for their color, flavour,

smokiness, texture, spiciness, and sweetness. A five-point hedonic scale was used, where 1 meant dislike very much and 5 meant like very much (Ruicong et al, 2016).

Analytical Methods

Oil absorption: the oil absorption rate was determined in duplicates by weighing the chips before and after frying.

Moisture: the moisture content was determined using the oven method (AOAC, 1984) with 5 g sample sizes in triplicate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Deep fat frying is commonly described as a mass transfer procedure in which moisture exits the food capillaries due to the high temperature of the frying oil, and the oil occupies some of these spaces via capillary forces. Potato crisps were fried in oils heated to 190°C, 200°C, and 210°C. The amount of fat absorbed varied based on the frying temperature and time, and it reduced as the frying temperature increased. The most important factor influencing the amount of fat absorbed by potato crisps was the frying temperature. Fat that is absorbed by potato slices during frying, in which increasing the temperature of frying increased the water evaporation rate reducing the length of frying and the amount of fat absorbed (Baumann and Escher, 1995). The observed association between the oil content of potato crisps and frying temperature differed from that seen by other writers, who discovered that increasing oil temperature increased the amount of oil absorbed by potato chips (Gamble et al., 1987). It was also found that temperatures between 150°C and 180°C had nearly no impact on the

amount of oil absorbed by the food product (Guillaumin, 1988). From colour and texture analysis of the fried chips at 190°C, 200°C, and 210°C for 70s and 80s each it was found that chips fried at 190°C for time t_1 had a better perception.

Figure 2: oil absorption rate after frying for t_1 time

Figure 3: Oil absorption rate after frying for t_2 time

The sun-dried chips showed lesser moisture content of around 2-3% resulting in the findings coinciding with the oil absorption rate being lesser resulting in a low-fat fried product.

Concerning the sensory evaluation (colour, flavour, smokiness, spiciness, and sweetness) of three different barbeque seasoning formulations SS1, SS2, and SS3 along with a commercial chips sample

taken as control. The results for overall liking revealed that the variation SS3 had the most appreciated sensorial score, with statistical significance and the scores of the chips evaluated at the end of the study period are given in Figure 4. One of the important sensorial attributes of the chips is the texture and this varied with each seasoning formulation. All the variations were perceived differently even though the chips were all fried at the same temperature and time, at 190°C for 70 seconds (t_1) as per the results from the trials done for the optimization of time and temperature. The highest score in flavour, spiciness, and sweetness (taste) was obtained for SS3 samples. According to the panelists, no significant differences were observed between the colour of the chips of all variations even after oil spraying before coating the barbeque seasoning as the seasoning powder applied to the hot oil sprayed potato chips, melts the powder and coats the chips evenly (Ainsworth & Plunkett, 2007). The cumulative overall acceptability between the three variants of barbecue seasoned potato chips that were fried at 190°C for 70 seconds (t_1) is given below.

Figure 4: Sensory analysis of Barbeque seasoned potato chips

CONCLUSION

The results obtained from this study suggest that sun-dried potato chips had a lesser moisture content and hence lesser oil absorption at a temperature of not below 190 giving a better perception of sensory attributes with the barbecue seasoning with no chemical pre-treatments.

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